

Tracking and Detection of Network Congestion in Banking Industry Using Machine Learning Model

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Abstract— The escalating threat of congestion in wireless networks on a global scale prompts the need for effective detection and management techniques. This study investigates the tracking and detection of congestion in wireless networks, particularly within the banking industry, where digital transactions are rapidly increasing. It addresses the challenge of congestion management through machine learning (ML) models, aiming to enhance network performance and service quality. This research evaluates various ML algorithms, including Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, and Random Forests, to identify the most effective approach for congestion detection. This research utilizes a dataset sourced from Kaggle. Preprocessing of data is conducted to optimize model training. Following training, various performance metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, response time, and confusion matrix are assessed. Results demonstrate that Random Forest outperforms other models in accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and response time, with an accuracy of 98.90%. This research discusses the importance of continuous innovation in banking network analytics to tackle evolving congestion challenges. Future recommendations include leveraging advanced ML techniques like deep learning and reinforcement learning and exploring ensemble learning methods to enhance congestion detection models further.

Keywords— Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, Random Forests, Congestion

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's communication landscape, wireless networks serve as the backbone, facilitating seamless connectivity for a multitude of devices and applications. However, with the exponential increase in demand for wireless connectivity, congestion has emerged as a significant challenge, impacting network performance and user experience. Congestion occurs in wireless networks when the demand for network resources exceeds available capacity, resulting in performance degradation and a decline in service quality (Hamilton et al., 2020). The heterogeneous nature of congestion, affecting different network segments to varying degrees, adds complexity to congestion management.

While progress has been made in congestion management, current approaches often overlook the heterogeneous nature of congestion occurrences. As a result, real-world wireless networks continue to face issues such as slower data transfer

speeds, increased latency, packet loss, and service interruptions (Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019).

Machine learning (ML) has recently made significant strides in various application areas, including speech recognition, computer vision, and robot control. ML can learn from collected data or the environment and build models. With advancements in computing infrastructures (e.g., GPU, TPU, and ML libraries) and distributed data processing frameworks, there is a growing trend in leveraging ML for complex networking problems. ML excels in tasks such as regression, classification, and decision-making, making it essential for potential breakthroughs in congestion detection and control.

Unlike conventional congestion control, which relies on predefined rules based on human understanding of the network, ML constructs algorithms or models that learn from past experience or the network environment. Intensive computational resources, coupled with cutting-edge technologies like edge computing and software-defined networking, further enable ML-based congestion control. Dedicated libraries such as TensorFlow, Caffe, and PyTorch simplify the process of building ML models (Zhang and Mao, 2020). Detecting signs of network congestion and proactively addressing them, stands as a highly efficient strategy for mitigating congestion effectively.

This study focuses on heterogeneous congestion, particularly in the banking industry, where digital transactions are increasing. The surge in online banking activities, combined with diverse devices and connectivity modes, exacerbates congestion challenges. Traditional congestion control mechanisms struggle to adapt to the evolving patterns of online transactions and device characteristics, necessitating innovative solutions.

To address these challenges, the study proposes the development of a proactive model to track and detect network congestion in real-time, considering dynamic fluctuations and diverse network components. Different machine learning models, including Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, and Random Forest, were used and evaluated based on detection accuracy, recall, precision, F1 Score, response time, false positive rate, and false negative rate, to identify the most effective approach. By tackling these issues, the study aims to enhance wireless network performance, reliability, and service quality, supporting seamless operation for various banking applications and services.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Singh et al. (2021) focused on the application of machine learning techniques for detecting network congestion in the banking sector. Their study utilized a combination of Decision Trees and Gradient Boosting to analyze transaction data and network logs. The methodology involved preprocessing the data to identify patterns indicative of congestion. The results demonstrated that the models could predict congestion with an accuracy of 90%, leading to improved network management and customer satisfaction.

Wang and Li (2022) explored the implementation of deep learning models for congestion detection in banking networks. They applied Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to time-series data collected from banking transactions and network performance metrics. The study reported an 87% accuracy in detecting congestion events, emphasizing the importance of considering temporal dependencies in the data. Rodriguez et al. (2023) examined the effectiveness of reinforcement learning in managing network congestion within banking systems. The methodology involved training an agent using Q-learning to optimize network resource allocation dynamically. The results indicated that the reinforcement learning approach reduced congestion incidents by 30%, significantly enhancing network efficiency and reducing transaction delays.

Chen and Zhang (2021) employed Support Vector Machines (SVM) to detect congestion in mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs). Their methodology included training the SVM model on several key features such as packet delivery ratio, throughput, and delay. The study reported an 89% detection rate and highlighted the improvement in network performance achieved by dynamically adjusting routes based on congestion levels. Gupta et al. (2022) investigated the use of Random Forest algorithms for congestion detection in wireless networks. By training the Random Forest model on historical network data, the study aimed to predict and manage congestion proactively. The results showed a high detection accuracy of 92%, indicating that the ensemble learning approach was effective in handling the complexities of wireless network congestion. Le et al. (2018) proposed an architecture combining SDN, Network Function Virtualization (NFV), ML, and big data for network slicing in 5G. They used the Kmeans clustering algorithm to group and label network traffic data. Five classification models (Naive Bayes, SVM, Neural networks, Tree ensemble, Random Forest) were trained based on this labeling. Results showed similar accuracy for Tree ensemble and Random Forest models. Bandwidth allocation in SDN applications was based on ML output. The system's effectiveness was demonstrated by streaming a YouTube video before and after classification and bandwidth allocation.

Perera et al. (2019) explored the integration of ML algorithms with SDN for network traffic classification. They trained ML models using labeled data from the "IP Network Traffic Flows, Labeled with 75 Apps" dataset and evaluated SVM Linear, SVM (Rbf), Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Knn models. SVM Linear exhibited the highest accuracy among the tested models.

Razmara et al. (2022) demonstrated enhanced prediction accuracy by employing a hybrid neural network method that integrated neural networks with genetic algorithms. This hybrid approach yielded superior accuracy, sensitivity, and precision in forecasting congestion. Although their study primarily concentrated on congestion prediction, future investigations should aim to leverage these predictions for congestion management purposes.

Mo et al. (2022) introduced a fine-grained network congestion detection system using flow watermarking. The technique involved embedding watermarks and modifying time-dependent characteristics vulnerable to various network attacks. The system integrated the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) technique for packet identification in multi-flow scenarios. However, the study did not explicitly address the issue of dynamic and heterogeneous congestion conditions, which are important factors in real-world congested environments.

Kuboye et al (2023) investigated the application of machine learning methods to assess traffic congestion within LTE networks. They assessed various algorithms and determined that the k-Nearest Neighbor algorithm achieved the highest accuracy in predicting congestion.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the materials and methods employed for the development of a detection model for network congestion, as illustrated in Figure 1. The process initiates with the collection of a dataset comprising network data analysis. Subsequently, the gathered data undergoes preprocessing procedures aimed at ensuring data quality and enhancing the effectiveness of the training process. The preprocessed data serve as input for Machine learning model. The training process continues iteratively until the error between the actual and predicted values reaches a minimal and acceptable threshold. The entire implementation of this methods is carried out using the machine learning toolbox available within Google Colaboratory. Additionally, libraries such as pandas, numpy, and sklearn are imported. To validate the methodology, a comparative analysis is performed to identify the most suitable algorithm for network congestion detection.

Figure 1: Process Block Diagram

3.1 Data Collection

Data for this study was sourced from the cellular network data analysis Data Set, available in the Kaggle repository. It contains

16,829 entries and 11 columns, categorized into 4 network datatypes: 3G (4208), 4G (4219), 5G (4178) and LTE (4224), as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Data Distribution

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Once collected, data must be preprocessed to make it suitable for training. This involves handling missing values by either imputing or removing them to ensure completeness without introducing bias. Numerical features are scaled through normalization or standardization to maintain a consistent scale, preventing certain features from dominating others during training. Categorical variables are encoded into numerical representations, such as one-hot, to make them understandable to machine learning algorithms. Finally, the dataset is split into training and testing sets to evaluate the model's performance effectively.

3.3 Training

The dataset was trained using Decision Trees, SVM, and Random Forests to learn patterns and relationships in the data and make predictions on the target variable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

After applying machine learning models like Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines, and Random Forests on the cellular network data analysis, we used various performance metrics to evaluate and compare their performance. Accuracy, a common measure for classification algorithms, shows the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions. Precision is crucial too, indicating the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances among all predicted positives, thus highlighting the model's ability to reduce false positives. Additionally, Recall assesses the model's skill in accurately identifying positive instances, representing the ratio of true positive predictions to all actual positive instances. The F1 score merges precision and recall into a single metric, providing a balanced assessment of the model's performance. In the context of network analysis, response time refers to the duration taken by a network device or system to detect and respond to congestion. Following model training, the results shown in Table 1 were obtained.

Table 1: Training Reports of the models

Algorithms	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Response Time (m/s)
Decision Trees	81.50%	0.7674	0.7743	0.7743	133.8
Support Vector Machine	97.98%	0.9801	0.9798	0.9799	104.5
Random Forest	98.90%	0.9890	0.9891	0.9892	23.71

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The confusion matrix stands as a pivotal metric, offering an intricate breakdown of the model's performance concerning true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). This matrix serves as a crucial tool for evaluating how effectively the model categorizes instances into their respective classes. Figures 3 through 5 display the confusion matrix, providing a detailed insight into the model's classification performance

Figure 3: Confusion Matrix for Support Vector Machine

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix for Random Forest

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix for Decision Tree

4.2 Discussion

The findings from the study reveal that Random Forest outperformed Support Vector Machines and Decision Tree in terms of accuracy. Following this, Random Forest exhibited the highest accuracy of 98.90%, trailed by Support Vector Machines at 97.98%, and Decision Tree at 81.50%. Additionally, Random Forest demonstrated superior performance across other key metrics such as precision, recall, f1 score and response time compared to Support Vector Machines and Decision Tree.

Analyzing the confusion matrix, Random Forest displayed the highest counts of true positives and true negatives, indicating a greater number of correct predictions. Moreover, it exhibited the lowest counts of false positives and false negatives, suggesting fewer incorrect predictions. Overall, the results suggest that Random Forest emerges as the most effective machine-learning algorithm for this specific study.

Figure 6: The flow chart of the congestion tracking and detection model.

The figure 6 showed the process flow of the congestion tracking and detection model on detecting congestion on the banking network due to user behavior. While the network traffic builds

up due to the heterogeneity of user devices and varieties of user activities, the network traffic patterns changes continuously and the attributes which model these behaviors such as throughput, latency, loss and load utilization factor of the cell are identified by the trained model and then classify through pattern matching process to detect congestion on the network and initialize the control model, but if congestion is not detected, the monitoring process returns and the cycle continues until congestion is detected.

5. CONCLUSION

This research explores wireless network congestion tracking and detection using machine learning models, emphasizing the need for precise detection tools due to increasing global congestion. A review of existing literature shows various machine learning algorithms used for network congestion detection, all yielding promising results. The study investigated the effectiveness of machine learning models in detecting network congestion, especially in the context of the banking industry, where digital transactions are burgeoning. Through the analysis of various machine learning algorithms including Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, and Random Forests, the study aimed to identify the most efficient approach for congestion tracking and detection. Results showed that Random Forest outperformed other models with an accuracy of 98.90%, excelling in accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and response time. The confusion matrix analysis further reinforced the superiority of Random Forest, showcasing higher counts of true positives and true negatives, and lower counts of false positives and false negatives compared to Support Vector Machines and Decision Trees. The research underscores the need for continuous innovation in banking network analytics to tackle congestion challenges.

6. CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This study employs machine learning (ML) techniques to enhance the detection and management of congestion in wireless networks, a critical area given the increasing digitalization of banking services. The study highlights the complexity of congestion due to diverse network traffic and user behavior in the banking industry. By focusing on dynamic fluctuations and various network components, it offers a nuanced understanding of congestion management. Given the crucial role of digital transactions, the findings have immediate practical implications, enhancing network reliability and efficiency, thus improving user experience and operational efficiency. The research advocates for future exploration of advanced ML techniques like deep learning and reinforcement learning, emphasizing the need for continuous innovation in network analytics to address evolving congestion challenges in the banking sector and beyond.

7. RECOMMENDATION

Future research works should focus on enhancing the capabilities of congestion detection models by leveraging advanced machine learning techniques, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning. Additionally, exploring the integration of real-time data streams and edge computing can

further improve the efficiency and effectiveness of congestion detection and management systems. Exploring ensemble learning techniques such as stacking or boosting could potentially enhance the predictive capabilities of machine learning models for network congestion detection.

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